

ARTISTIC INTERPRETATION OF SOCIAL NATIONAL PSYCHOLOGY IN THE NOVEL "SAROB"

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8005571>

Orifjonova Zilola Rasuljonovna

Termiz State Pedagogical Institute

Uzbek language and literature, 2nd stage master's student

Abstract.

This article is devoted to comparing the psychologism in the works of Uzbek and American writers in both Uzbek and English literature. In the works of both writers, the tragic fate of the heroes who could not adapt to their psychology is captured. The novels being compared depict two different national psychologies that are drastically different from each other. National psychology is more focused on family issues

Keywords.

Psychologism, stories, novel, protagonist, symbolic, classical, brevity, mirage.

Abdullah Kahhor writes that psychology is the most important aspect of writing skills. A work of art is a beautiful vision of life, a product of the writer's artistic thinking. In every work of art, first of all, a call to goodness is put forward, to love and appreciate life, to overcome various difficulties and hardships with patience. According to the words of the honored writer O'tkir Hoshimov, a true work is not written, but born. In every written work, the writer describes his emotional experiences, sufferings, talents, dreams, as well as the pains and problems of the nation and the people, combining them with the spirit of artistry in the form of characters and characters. The longevity of the work is distinguished by how it psychologically illuminates the images and characters that reveal the idea of the work. The reader who gets hold of the novel "Mirage" sees the happy future of Saidi and Munish Khan, full of warm, transparent dreams, full of love. They bravely overcome all the obstacles in their life (in a work of art)... After all, good people are also in life

He says that he achieves good goals in artistic works... But in the development of the events of the work, this opinion turns into a mirage, just like the happiness of Saidi and Munisa Khan. Saidiy is a well-educated, knowledgeable, talented, restrained young man, the owner of a strong emotional heart, who can see the world with clear deep eyes. But he does not open his heart to anyone, he thinks a

lot - he speaks so little, as if there is another Saidi inside him. He has friends who are generous and open-minded like Shafrin. They are ready to help Saidi in any situation. However, there was a wall that separated Saidi from everyone, even from his beloved daughter, Munish Khan, who was always by his side. The writer describes this in the course of the changes in Saidi's psyche during the development of the work. This is what he thinks when he sees Munishkhan for the first time. "... If this girl has a problem and the only one who can help her is Saidi..." Scientist Zik Mund from Wona applies Freud's concept of psychological dynamics to any person - that is, nothing in his character, in his life, is a coincidence. he writes that the reason will be solved. We can see the proof of this directly in the case of Saidi. No matter how honest, correct, and talented young man Sadi was, he lost his way in life, joined the ranks of nationalists and turned his endless talent into a puppet of his life. Neither in public life nor in personal life, he was able to achieve happiness. With her brother's insistence, Munish Khan marries Mukhtar Khan, whom she does not want. And Saidi marries Sora Khan, the only daughter of a teacher who is completely unsuitable for him. They force themselves to get used to that fate. As you know, overcome The warmth of love is palpable in the family that was created as a result of inevitable desire. In a family created out of obligation, the obligation to remain a family creates false feelings.

Abdulla Qahhor described the cases of Saidi and Munishkhan based on the dynamic, analytical and typological principle of psychologism. If the social system, deceived by the false ideas of some impure people in the system, Saidi dies at the end of the play. Munish Khan commits suicide. The fate of a person is not affected by the time and period in which he lived, the environment. In this regard, the essence of the psychodynamic approach is expressed in the idea that the person in the interpretation of Zik Mund Freud consists of a growing complex device of never-ending conflicting processes. rather, it means determined, that is, caused. In the psychodynamic direction, determinism applies equally to the events that we do, feel, or think, and even to the events that some people think are completely random, as well as to unknowingly speaking, unknowingly writing down mistakes, and all similar situations. This idea brings us to the most basic and analytical topic presented by the psychodynamic approach, namely, it is this idea that emphasizes the unconscious mental processes in the control of human behavior. Abdulla Qahhor's novel "Mirage" was considered by many writers of Uzbek and neighboring nations to be a school of skills for them. Those who have learned and are still learning from examples of deep psychological analysis in the work,

methods of character and situation creation, ways to achieve plot and compositional integrity, especially the appeal of artistic language.

Since its creation, the novel has not lost the attention of literary studies and is still the cause of heated debates. The works of literary critics O. Sharafiddinov, M. Koshjanov, U. Normatov, V. Smirnova, M. Sulstonova, who analyzed the ideological and artistic features of the work seriously and in detail, are significant achievements not only of literary studies, but also of Uzbek novel studies. However, the articles on "Sarob" did not go beyond the repeated assumptions about the history of the novel, the reasons that played a decisive role in the author's decision to do this work. In particular, when this issue is raised, our literary experts cite the following brief comment from A. Qahhor's "Answer to a Letter": "In the early 1930s, fate brought me face to face with bourgeois nationalists, who provoked my hatred and anger. , which upset my balance. I felt an insurmountable desire to awaken this feeling in others. As a result, the novel "Mirage" was created. The writer did not say anything else about how this encounter happened and its details. This fact alone has been accepted by most literary scholars as a sufficient reason for the creation of the novel, and their subsequent comments are a well-known consequence. In his 1965 article entitled "From a Life Incident to an Art Fabric", Adib recalls an interesting fact: I will never forget an incident that happened in connection with my story "The Headless Man", funny on the surface, but serious in essence... I wrote this story in 1929. At that time, I was working in "Yangi Fergana" newspaper published in Kok... The story was published in "Yer Yuzi" magazine. Shortly after that, I received a summons from the prosecutor's office. The prosecutor received me coldly, and when he believed that I was the one who wrote the story, he began to slander me. , – All writers are cowards! - he said... I could not speak to the prosecutor. I used this phenomenon in the novel "Mirage". Perhaps this event is not so random."

In our opinion, this "inherently serious incident" is exactly the incident of "facing the bourgeois nationalists" written in "Answer to a Letter". As we mentioned at the beginning, after the revolution, the intelligentsia began to be divided into "old" and "new", "our own" and "foreign", as a result, although the majority of intellectuals in the central cities were forced to go abroad, in the 20th until the end of the years, this policy did not take the scale of reaction, freedom of creativity and press, intellectual independence was relatively preserved. In the second half of the 1920s, especially from the beginning of the 1930s, coercion, orders, and centralized control increased in the sphere of ideology and creativity, just as in economic life. Comments on the shortcomings of the new system were

declared as "hostility to the system", and comments against moral backwardness as "slander of the poor". In the same years, the terms "pro-Islamism", "pro-Turkism", "nationalism", which were a support for the tsarist colonizers, began to be used again, and in the eyes of the corrupt authorities, the symbols of colonialism became a weapon against the thinking public. Dozens of extermination campaigns such as the "Group of Eighteen", the "Botu and Ramz" case, the "Inoghamovchikship", "Kasimovchikship", "Badrydinovchikship" are actually preliminary preparations for the 37th year, which Regardless of the field, the same "labels" are attached to all of them. If in 1930 there was a famous trial against Kasimov, the chairman of the Supreme Court of the Supreme Court of Uzbekistan, Sadulla Kasimov, then exactly two years later, the Chief Prosecutor of the Supreme Court of the Supreme Court of Uzbekistan Shamsiddin Badriddinov a new process took place that "exposed" badreligion under the leadership. We will discuss them in detail below.

Now, the newspaper "Uzbekistanskaya Pravda", which continuously covered the criminal trial, from May 11 to June 18, 1932, mentioned the fact several times (whether it is right or wrong is another matter!) we want to mention. Several people related to the newspaper "Yani Fergana" also testified in the court. From their testimony, it can be concluded that Badriddinovists have always interfered with the work of the newspaper, introduced their own people into its editorial office, harassed public reporters, did not publish their relevant articles, and even put pressure on their lives. In the same years, Abdulla Qahhor was preparing to write the novel "Sarab", studying the materials of another process similar to badridnovism. By itself, these statements related to "New Fergana" did not escape his attention, and the incident of "prosecutor's summons" that happened to him was "essentially serious" and "not so accidental". affected. On the other hand, "nationalism", "pan-Turkism", and "pan-Islamism" were the most infamous accusations related to both Kassimism and Badridism. This "proven" fact became the basis for A. Qahhor to evaluate the incident he was facing as a "clash with bourgeois nationalists". We will see the proof of this many more times below. Now I have to say an important comment, or rather, my opinion. The fact is that in the previous article entitled "Three Mirages" ("Yoshlik" No. 6, 1986) I made a number of correct conclusions based on my artistic and historical imagination, knowledge and the nature of the sources at hand at that time. at the same time, I have expressed some controversial opinions that need to be edited now. First of all, in this article, the reasons for the writing of the novel "Mirage" were not revealed, only the process of its processing was paid attention to. In this case, too, the scope of criticism of the novel blocked the original essence from our eyes, started us on the

path of a one-sided approach, and as a result, I switched to looking for the reason for every change and editing from wrong criticism. However, a logical question should always keep us awake: if the reason for the changes was only the criticism of the years of repression, why was A. Qahhor not forced to rewrite "Sarob" in those years? Why was it published only in 1957? made changes to the second edition of the novel At that time the repression was almost over!

We should now ask ourselves these and dozens of other questions and seek impartial answers to them. The truth about the era, about the poet and his works, no matter how bitter, must be openly told and subjected to scientific analysis, otherwise the chain of incomplete truths will exclude us from the future. We said that A. Qahhor was seriously studying similar sources while the trial of Boya Badriddinov was taking place. So, what were those materials? In the course of further research, I turned to a number of literatures kept in the house-museum of A. Qahhor. They are P. Alekseyenkov's book "Kokandskaya autonomiya" ("Kokan autonomy"), the book "Udar po natsionalisticheskoy kontrrevolyusii" ("A blow to counter-revolutionary nationalism"), which illuminates the process of "Kasimovism", and the state prosecutor R. Katanyan's work in this process. The book "Protiv Kasimova, protiv kasimovshini" ("against Kasimov and Kasimovchilik") is a complete collection of the impeachment speech. It is important that the writer carefully read all three books, during the reading he drew lines in red and green ink, red, purple and black pencils, made short notes He wrote comments, and after reading, he also recorded the dates. In particular, he dated the last page of the book "Kokandskaya Autonomy" as "Kakharov 28/11.31" and the other two books as "Abdulla 18/1 U.32". At the time when Adib was reading these books, he was in full swing at the Kafanov club in Tashkent. So, what is the relationship between these court proceedings and the Kokand Autonomous Region to the novel "Sarob". Unfortunately, the articles published so far have not answered these questions. As if in the 1920s, really strong nationalist organizations were doing extensive work, they were constantly corrupting young people like Saidi under their influence, not backing down from any dirty crimes against the state and the people, and in the end, the victorious Shura regime As a result of his righteous struggle, his goals were turned into a mirage. Literary studies, mainly reflecting on the reworked version of the novel (except for O. Sharafiddinov!), does not even remember the modern ideological tones of the original version, the important places that were later removed. As a result, abstract concepts, various rumors, and mutually exclusive hypotheses about the vital foundations, reasons for creation, and prototypes of the novel "Sarob" claim instead of the truth.

If we take into account the socio-political environment at the time the novel was written, the objective reality that influenced the writer, the ideology that shaped the writer and the factors that nurtured his aesthetic views, we think that we have approached the problem concretely. It is not surprising that the documents of that period studied by A. Qakhor, the writer's personal books, and the marks written on the pages by a writer's pen guide us in revealing its essence.

REFERENCES:

1. S.L. Rubinstein. Uchenie o caractere/Otryvok iz monografii S.L. Rubinshteyn "Osnovy obshchey psichologii" (<https://www.psychology-online.net/articles/doc-451.html>)
2. Barabash O.V. Psychologism as a constructive component of the poetic novel L.N. Tolstoy "Anna Karenina": dissertation ... candida filologicheskikh nauk. - Moscow, 2008 (<http://www.dslib.net/russkaja-literatura/psihologizm-kak-konstruktivnyj-komponent-pojetiki-romana-l-n-tolstogo-anna.html>).
3. Kuronov D. Introduction to literary studies. - A.: X,ayot publishing house, 2002.
4. Umurov X,. Artistic psychology and modern Uzbek novel. - T., Science, 1983.
5. N. Kobilova. Artistic psychology in the works of Jack London and Abdulla Kakhkhor. Philol. Dr. Yu[^]iss. - Bukhara, 2020.